

Online data supplement

Dual GIPR and GLP-1R agonist tirzepatide inhibits aeroallergen-induced allergic airway inflammation in mouse model of obese asthma.

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METHODS

Mice

TALLYHO/JngJ (TALLYHO) mice were obtained from Jackson Laboratories (*Bar Harbor, ME*). The animals were maintained in a temperature-controlled room at 22.2°C on a half day light-dark cycle. Mice were fed a regular diet (PicoLab® Laboratory Rodent Diet 5L0D) and tap water was available ad libitum. Eleven- to thirteen-week-old male TALLYHO mice were used for experiments. Animal experiments were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee at Vanderbilt University Medical Center and were conducted according to the guidelines for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals prepared by the Institute of Laboratory Animal Resources, National Research Council.

Incretin mimetic drugs treatment and Alt-Ext-challenge in mouse model

[D-Ala²]-GIP (Tocris, Minneapolis, MN), semaglutide (Novo Nordisk Inc., Bagsvaerd, Denmark), tirzepatide (MedChemExpress LLC, Monmouth Junction, NJ), and the vehicle (2% DMSO/saline) were administered subcutaneously every 3 days from day 0 to day 12. The dose of incretin mimetic drugs was 25 nmol/kg on day 0, and 50 nmol/kg on day 3, 6, 9, and 12. Twenty-four hours after the last treatment, a glucose tolerance test (GTT) was performed. In the aeroallergen-induced asthma model, 8 µg (protein amount) of *Alternaria alternata* extract (Alt-Ext) (Stallergenes Greer, Lenoir, NC) in 80 µl of PBS or 80 µl of PBS as vehicle were administered intranasally 4 hours after the drug treatment on day 3, 6, 9, and 12. The mice were euthanized and then bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF), whole lungs, and serum were harvested 24 h after the last challenge of Alt-Ext or PBS.

In the therapeutic intervention model (Figure S5A), Alt-Ext or PBS was administered intranasally on day 0. Then the incretin mimetic drugs (50 nmol/kg) were administered subcutaneously on day 3, 6, and 9, and Alt-Ext or PBS was administered intranasally 4 hours after the drug treatment on day 3, 6, and 9. The mice were euthanized and then BALF and whole lungs were harvested 24 h after the last challenge of Alt-Ext or PBS.

Glucose tolerance test

Twenty-four hours after last drug treatment, the mice were fasted for 6 h prior to a glucose tolerance test (GTT). An equivalent amount of dextrose (1.5g/kg of the average body weight of tirzepatide treated group) was injected intraperitoneally to mice in all groups. The blood glucose level was measured before and after the dextrose injection by Contour next test strips and Contour next EZ meter according to the manufacturer's instructions (Ascensia Diabetes Care, Parsippany, NJ). The area under the curve (AUC) of GTT was calculated by GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA).

ELISA

DuoSet ELISA kits (eotaxin (CCL11), eotaxin-2 (CCL24), KC (CXCL1), LIX (CXCL5), MDC (CCL22), TARC (CCL17), IL-6 and IL-33), Quantikine® ELISA (IL-1 β , IL-4, IL-10, and IL-17) from R&D Inc. (Minneapolis, MN), and mouse uncoated ELISA kit (IL-5 and IL-13) from ThermoFisher scientific (Waltham, MA) were used to measure the concentration of cytokines and chemokines in BALF or lung homogenates according to manufacturer's instructions. Mouse leptin ELISA kit (ThermoFisher scientific) was used to measure the concentration of leptin in mouse serum.

Values of ELISA below the detection limit were assigned a value at half of the lower limit of detection to allow for statistical analysis.

Anti-Alt-Ext- or anti-tirzepatide-specific IgG1 in serum was detected by ELISA according to previous studies.^{1,2} Briefly, 96 well plates were coated with 10 ug protein of Alt-Ext, 20 ug of tirzepatide in 100ul of PBS and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The plate was washed with PBS containing 0.05% tween-20 and subsequently blocked with 1% BSA/PBS for 1 h. In addition, non-coated plate was prepared to test the false positive by non-specific binding of serum Ig. Each serum was serially diluted and added to the wells of Alt-Ext-, tirzepatide-, or non-coated plate. The plates were incubated overnight at 4 °C. The plates were washed, and biotin conjugated anti-mouse IgG1 antibody (1 ug/mL) (RMG1-1, Biolegend) was added and incubated at room temperature (RT) for 1 hour. The plates were washed, and streptavidin-HRP (R&D) was added and incubated at RT for 30 min. The plates were washed, and HRP substrate TMB (R&D) was added and incubated at RT for 30 min. Then stop solution (2N H₂SO₄) was added, and optical density (OD) is defined in dual wavelength mode 450/650 nm. Each anti-Alt-Ext specific IgG1 and anti-tirzepatide specific IgG1 was calculated as OD (Alt-Ext-coated plate – non-coated plate) and OD (tirzepatide-coated plate – non-coated plate) respectively.

Cell differentials

Cytospin preparations of BALF cells were performed for each sample. The slides were stained with a Richard-Allan Scientific Three step stain kit (ThermoFisher scientific) to determine cell differentials. Differential counts were based on counting 300 cells per slide.

Flow cytometry

The harvested lungs were minced and digested with collagenase IV (1 mg/ml, SIGMA-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) and DNase I (5 IU/ml, SIGMA-Aldrich) in RPMI1640 with 5% FBS for 45 minutes at 37 °C and a single cell suspension was obtained by grinding and passing the digested lung through a 70 µm cell strainer. The lung cells were stained with antibodies for cell surface markers after hemolysis. In the different experiments to detect transcription factors, the cells were fixed and permeabilized by Foxp3/Transcription Factor Staining Buffer Set (TONBO Biosciences, San Diego, CA), and intracellularly stained for transcription factors. Antibodies used for flow cytometry are shown in Table S1. All samples were measured on a BD LSR II Flow Cytometer and analyzed using FlowJo Software.

Airway responsiveness (AR) measurement

Twenty-four hours after the last challenge of Alt-Ext or PBS, TALLYHO mice treated with incretin mimetics drugs or the vehicle were anaesthetized with pentobarbital sodium (120 mg/kg), and a tracheostomy tube was placed in the trachea of mice. Mice were then mechanically ventilated using the FlexiVent FX2 system (SCIREQ, Montreal, QC Canada) with 150 breaths/min and a tidal volume of 10 ml/kg. Airway resistance was determined after administration of increasing doses of nebulized acetyl-b-methacholine (0, 6.25, 12.5, 25, and 50 mg/ml).

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed with GraphPad Prism 9. In metabolism tests, timeline data were analyzed by using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey-multiple pairs comparisons test. Statistical significances between treatment groups were assessed by one-way ANOVA with Tukey-multiple pairs comparisons test, or Mann-Whitney test for two group comparison. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant between two groups.

REFERENCES

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Table S1. List of Antibodies for flow cytometry

Antigen	Fluorochrome	Clone	Supplier
CD3	violetFluor™ 450	17A2	TONBO Biosciences
CD4	PE-Cy7	RM4-5	BD Pharmingen™
CD45	redFluor™ 710	30-F11	TONBO Biosciences
CD278 (ICOS)	APC	C398.4A	eBioscience™
Foxp3	PE	FJK-16s	eBioscience™
GATA3	PE-CF594	L50-823	BD Pharmingen™
RORγt	PerCP-Cy5.5	Q31-378	BD Pharmingen™
ST2 (IL-33R)	BV711	U29-93	BD Pharmingen™
Lineage cell detection cocktail-biotin (mouse)	(Biotin)		Miltenyi Biotech Inc.
Streptoavidin-APC-Cy7	APC-Cy7		BioLegend
Ghost UV450	UV450		TONBO Biosciences